

Summary of needs definition through Design Thinking workshops

D5.1

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D5.1: Summary of needs definition through Design Thinking workshops

Due date:

31/03/2021

Actual submission date:

12/07/2021

Project start date:

01/01/2020

Duration:

36 months

Work Package concerned:

WP5

Concerned work package leader:

BE participation

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Authors:

Marzia Mazzonetto, Maïté Debry - BE participation

Ignace Adant, Joaquin Landazuri Benitez - ELI-UCLouvain

Contributors (members of the Brussels cluster who contributed to the process described in this deliverable):

Marzia Mazzonetto, Maïté Debry - BE participation

Ignace Adant, Joaquin Landazuri Benitez - ELI-UCLouvain

Nelawu Malanda - Innoviris

Disclaimer

This report reflects only the authors' view. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N° 872687

Table of contents

1. TRANSFORM and its key concepts	5
1.1 Description of the TRANSFORM project	5
1.2 The key pillars of the Brussels-Capital region cluster activities in the TRANSFORM project	6
1.3 Timeline of the Brussels-Capital region (BCR) cluster activities	8
2. Design-Thinking applied to innovation for the circular economy: an exploratory process of the Brussels-Capital Region	10
2.1 DT: five stages as key milestones for a collective dynamic process	11
2.2 Applying DT to RRI and circular economy in the BCR	13
2.3 Responsibly innovating in circular economy: the path to the Spheres pilot	21
3. Spheres, the pilot action developed by the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital cluster	23
4. Community assessment of the Spheres approach	27
4.1 Workshop with Think Tank members	27
4.1.1 Welcome and workshop introduction	27
4.1.2 Agenda	28
4.1.3 Participants	28
4.1.4 Summary and outcomes of the workshop	30
4.2 Workshop with civil society organisations representatives	41
4.2.1 Agenda and aim of the workshop	41
4.2.2 Participants	42
4.2.3 Summary and outcomes of the workshop	43
4.3 Summary of key outcomes of community assessment	48
5. Conclusions and steps ahead	50
Bibliography	55

1. TRANSFORM and its key concepts

1.1 Description of the TRANSFORM project

TRANSFORM is an H2020 EU-funded project (2020-2022) that brings together three European regions – Lombardy (Italy), Brussels-Capital (Belgium) and Catalonia (Spain), pairing with a co-creation initiative (CC-PES) in Boston (USA). There are 12 partners in the consortium.

TRANSFORM introduces citizen engagement practices into the governance of regional Research and Innovation (R&I) dealing in particular with S3 (Smart Specialisation Strategies). S3 focuses on the strengths and competitive advantages that territories like regions have, to encourage growth, jobs and prosperity through local partnerships.

Under the common framework of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), each region runs participatory activities aimed at implementing open and inclusive processes that make local R&I priorities more connected to societal needs, while generating socially acceptable solutions through the involvement of quadruple helix (4-helix) stakeholders (business, research, civil society and public administration).

The TRANSFORM project is part of a long tradition of projects funded by the European Union, aimed at linking science and society (Science with and for Society - SwafS). TRANSFORM is also part of a group of 11 projects that have been funded over the past 3 years, under the same framework of action, projects where the involvement of public authorities is seen as key to change.¹

¹ The framework of action is 'Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation - TOPIC ID: [SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020](#)'

1.2 The key pillars of the Brussels-Capital region cluster activities in the TRANSFORM project

In line with the project's main objectives, the Brussels-Capital region (BCR) activities have been developed around five main pillars that have inspired the cluster's approach for its pilot. These pillars are:

1. CO-DESIGN AND CO-CREATION - these methodological approaches allow the establishment of participatory processes involving various stakeholders and can be easily adapted to different contexts. The expertise that partners bring together in the TRANSFORM project is strongly focused on these two approaches. In the BCR cluster these methodological approaches are seen as strong potential boosters of creativity and key information to make R&I more innovative and connected to society.

2. COLLECTIVE INTELLIGENCE - co-design and co-creation allow collective intelligence to emerge from participatory processes. Collective intelligence makes it possible, among other things, to anticipate and better understand the potential impacts of innovations and research, it can bring creativity, and above all bring out knowledge that can be very useful for innovation itself, or the definition of policies and regulations around innovation.

3. The QUADRUPLE-HELIX INVOLVEMENT - is also key to the responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach adopted by the European Commission and by the BCR. It is about involving all relevant stakeholders in the processes: citizens and civil society, public institutions and operators, the university sector, businesses and the private sector. This makes innovations more efficient, sustainable and socially responsible.

4. STRENGTHENING THE CURRENT KNOWLEDGE BASE - in an R&I process, the work of capturing collective intelligence is rarely put in place, and key stakeholders are often not involved. Multi-stakeholder (4-helix) processes are key to the BCR cluster activities, including impact assessment of the added value brought about by such types of practices. Building on the existing R&I knowledge base, including the exploitation of existing collective intelligence elements around topics of interest, is at the core of the cluster activities.

5. CONTRIBUTING TO S3 (Smart Specialization Strategies) - S3 priorities for increasing the innovation potential of the regions involved in the project are at the heart of TRANSFORM.

The BCR is currently working on the renovation of its S3 planning for the period 2021-2027. Innoviris, the public agency in charge of this process, has created a Steering Committee formed of various stakeholders and organisations representing different sectors (construction, finance, universities, environment, statistics). The methodology used for the renewal of the S3 consisted in:

- Defining societal challenges
- Mapping the local Research, Development, and Innovation ecosystem. The Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP) was used in this context.

These two processes led to a map of Strategic Innovation Domains to prioritize. The purpose was to build a flexible and agile S3 approach, having the capacity to change current sectors, while considering bottom-up needs as well as top-down priorities. The strategy considered global trends including the Sustainable Development Goals, the Green Deal and Horizon Europe Mission areas.

The societal challenges that have been highlighted so far by this process in the Brussels-Capital region are:

1. *Climate and Energy*: reduction of emissions from mobility, construction and industry; biodiversity; energy efficiency of buildings and enterprises; renewable energy and smart grids.
2. *Resources optimisation*: Circular Economy, e-waste management, eco-design, industrial symbiose, economy of functionality; BeinT (digitalisation of enterprises - small and medium)
3. *Inclusive and representative society*: addressing social inequalities; social and cooperative economy and innovation; addressing the digital gap focusing on e-inclusion; inclusive public space and homing; participative and representative governance.
4. *Health & well-being*: personalised health care; med/lifetech, e-health; more sophisticated diagnostics and therapies; new organisation of care; epidemics management.
5. *Healthy Food for all*: sustainable, healthy, and safe food systems; ecological and circular urban agriculture; healthy and sustainable alternative food products
6. *Mobility*: new form and systems of urban transport; modal shift and mobility-as-a-service; focus on urban logistic and distribution.

Altogether, these societal challenges and their accompanying S3 strategies aim to define the future economy of the BCR that should be competitive, digital, sustainable, resilient, and

inclusive. Reflections around these 6 pillars have been part of the work which has led to the definition of the region's pilot activities within the TRANSFORM project.

1.3 Timeline of the Brussels-Capital region (BCR) cluster activities

This section provides information on the phases and steps the BCR cluster implemented in year 1 of the TRANSFORM project and intends to implement in years 2 and 3:

January to December 2020:

- Design-Thinking approach applied to the Responsible Research and Innovation needs and challenges of the BCR R&I system.
- Mapping of existing RRI programs and activities in the Brussels-Capital region.

January to March 2021:

- Co-design of the BCR pilot activity on the theme of the circular economy, through the engagement of the actors of the 4-helix: public authorities, companies, universities and civil society organizations:
 - Creation of a Think Tank (multi-stakeholder group of local experts) to support the process of shared definition of indicators for the evaluation of the impact of pilot activities of the cluster.
 - Establishment of a network of non-profit organisations to be involved in the BCR TRANSFORM pilot activities focused on citizen engagement.
- Organisation of two online participatory workshops (with Think Tank members & civil society representatives) to better define the needs to be addressed through the project's local pilot activities.

April to July 2021:

- Launch of Spheres, the pilot activity co-designed by the BCR cluster through a Design-thinking process aiming to conduct open and inclusive processes to better connect local R&I to societal needs while involving 4-helix stakeholders.
- Launch of a call to select R&I projects that will receive support from the BCR TRANSFORM pilot.
- Co-design of the needs, resources, expectations and perceptions of the actors of the 4-helix with particular attention given to groups of citizens.

August 2021 to February 2022:

- Pilot activities aimed at assessing various types of innovations through a collective intelligence process with the engagement of 4-helix actors.

March to April 2022:

- Among the innovations assessed by the BCR TRANSFORM pilot, the cluster will select a short-list of innovations that will receive additional funding for their implementation phase and to be presented at the final TRANSFORM conference in 2022.

May to October 2022:

- Implementation of innovative solutions co-created by the short-listed R&I projects
- Collaboration with policy makers to ensure that solutions respond to public policy priorities and approaches, and that a policy commitment is taken and conceptual thinking processes and / or proposed solutions can be integrated into future policy actions.
- Impact assessment of the BCR TRANSFORM pilot activities, looking at the added-value of implementing more open and inclusive processes and better connecting local R&I to societal needs while involving 4-helix stakeholders

2. Design-Thinking applied to innovation for the circular economy: an exploratory process of the Brussels-Capital Region

The following section presents the results of the application of the Design-Thinking approach (DT) to analyze support mechanisms for innovation in the circular economy in the BCR. At this stage of the TRANSFORM project, the work carried out by the BCR cluster has had the following main objectives:

- to identify stakeholders' needs and R&I challenges in the development of the circular economy in the BCR;
- to identify and contextualise existing citizen engagement processes within R&I support mechanisms and initiatives in the field of circular economy in the BCR;
- to understand how to (e.g. through which "mechanisms") efficiently integrate stakeholders' needs and citizen engagement into the public governance of R&I so that they are met.

The DT approach relies on a set of (i) stages ("or steps") that allow for collaborative multi-stakeholder work to take place. These stages consist not only in identifying and defining problems but also in finding solutions. Finally (ii) it provides the possibility to go back and forth between different stages while putting together very different actors.

The BCR cluster has chosen this approach for multiple reasons, as explained at length in the project rationale (DoA), one of them being its high level of flexibility and adaptation to various contexts and objects. It can be applied to products or processes (which is the most frequent use of DT at a micro scale), but it can also be used to investigate 'macro' objects such as private or public innovation support systems for the circular economy of a given territory. This application of DT is, to the best of the cluster's knowledge, original. As it will be explained later, another element of originality of the BCR approach is the introduction of experimental sequencing of R&I – which will allow for a real assessment of innovation support systems of a given territory.

The specific context of the region is particularly favorable to the use of this method: the BCR, along with other Belgian and European regions, is committed to the values and benefits of RRI, hence its engagement in the TRANSFORM project and other RRI-related

EU-funded initiatives. These initiatives include for example the PRO-Ethics project² and the citizen engagement processes leading to the selection of the 100 European cities addressing the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Horizon Europe Mission. In the BCR, public authorities have also been carrying out multi-stakeholder engagement processes to identify needs and target areas of activity – including, but not only, the circular economy - for the territory and their smart specialization strategies.

In the following three chapters we will first provide an overview of the Design-Thinking approach ("2.1 DT: five stages as key milestones for a collective dynamic process"). We then explain the process that, through the collaborative work of the BCR cluster partners over several months, has led to the implementation of the DT within the framework of the TRANSFORM project by the Brussels cluster ("2.2. Applying DT to RRI and Circular Economy in the BCR"). Finally, we present the key results of this process ("2.3 Responsibly innovating in circular economy: the path to the Spheres pilot").

2.1 DT: five stages as key milestones for a collective dynamic process

The Design Thinking methodology is well known due to its human-centered approach to innovation. It solves complex issues by balancing people's needs, technological possibilities, and business opportunities (Brown, 2020).

The DT comprises 5 stages: empathize, define, ideate, prototype and test. These stages are briefly explained in this section, together with the main characteristics of the DT process. The content provided below contains references taken from the "Introduction to Design Thinking PROCESS GUIDE (2010)", together with additional contributors of other authors, such as Volpi, Opromolla and Medaglia (2019).

The DT process is not linear, it follows an interactive path between stages. The process is continuously moving among stages to reevaluate whether needs are properly met. The approach intrinsically promotes a continuous reformulation of the problem space and its solution. As a result, the process delivers not only a tested prototype to solve a wicked problem but also generates shared value for the people involved.

Empathize: it implies understanding people/organisations and their context. How are they doing things and why? What are their needs? How do they perceive the world? To do so, observation, conversation, watching and listening to people/organisations targeted is

² <https://pro-ethics.eu/>

necessary. By the end of the stage, information should be unpacked and shared with the team.

Before moving to the next stage, designers should be able to identify the main behaviors and needs of the people/organisations they will be designing a solution for. Moreover, these elements should be captured for a specific context and, ideally, they should be non-obvious findings.

Define: this stage is about bringing clarity and focus to the problem. During this stage, findings of the empathize process will be turned into insights. Insights are defined as “discoveries that you can leverage to tackle the design challenge”. A good strategy to identify these insights is to consider what stood out during the previous. By the end of this stage, an "actionable problem statement" should be developed, also known as point-of-view or POV. A POV is developed through the articulation of 3 elements:

- Users: understanding the type of user that is being addressed
- Needs: selecting the needs which are the most important to be fulfilled through the process of synthesizing of information.
- Insights: outcomes from the empathy stage together with research work

POVs should provide inspiration and empowerment (so they can take independent but parallel decisions) to the team, some type of criteria to evaluate ideas and a task that is not too broad to be undertaken.

Ideate: this stage consists in the generation of ideas. The main techniques used for ideation are brainstorming, building (prototyping), bodystorming, mind mapping and sketching. Along these options, some principles are advised to be maintained: go beyond obvious solutions, use teams' strengths and perspectives, explore unexpected areas, develop a diverse set of innovative options, discard obvious solutions, and defer judging .

This stage is based on creativity and imagination. All ideas are worth considering- the best idea may arrive from optimizing single shares of contributions.

Prototype: this stage comprises the development of a “low-resolution prototype”. The aim is to develop a prototype fast and cheaply, so that the user can try it out and provide feedback. The user should interact with the prototype so that efficiency and effectiveness is tested through this interaction.

It is recommended not to spend too much on the prototype and to get emotionally attached to it. Yet, it is important to define a variable to measure the interaction of the user with the prototype. Some questions that are generally useful when developing the prototype:

- what do you hope to test with the user?
- what sort of behaviors do you expect?

Prototyping and testing are intertwined, so the testing stage may come right after the development of the prototype.

Testing: during this stage users are asked to provide feedback on the prototype. This is an opportunity to understand the user better and therefore, empathize. Feedback should not be narrowed down to a yes or no question, but rather why questions, in order to continue learning about the user and the potential solution.

Testing is generally done through a physical object (that is used by potential users in their daily routines) or experiences (creating a location to present a real situation). Testing should be conducted respecting some basic principles:

- Let the users interact by themselves. Show but do not tell.
- Create experiences.
- Ask for comparisons between different prototypes.

The testing prototype will most likely take the process back to different stages such as: refine prototypes, learn about users (building empathy) and refine POVs. Even if the process looks linear, a design challenge can be addressed in various orders. *“Ultimately you will make the process your own and adapt it to your style and your work”.*

2.2 Applying DT to RRI and circular economy in the BCR

The Empathizing phase: knowledge sharing and problems identification

The TRANSFORM project partners involved in the BCR cluster have various types of expertise in RRI, circular economy, innovation and the specific context of smart specialization strategies in the region. They therefore represent a relevant multidisciplinary group of local stakeholders. Together, since the very start of the project they have focused on the Empathizing stage of the DT process, aimed to explore, put into perspective, and share perceptions and understandings of specific contexts, problems encountered and constraints on the development of RRI. This first step into the DT process focused on capitalizing on the partners' experience, their current scientific work and activities developed outside the TRANSFORM project and their know-how of citizen engagement and R&I governance. Each partner shared their specific expertise on:

- BE participation: RRI, citizen participation and engagement, inclusion.
- MAD Brussels: design thinking, social innovation, socially engaged and collaborative approach to design, engagement of designers.
- ELI-UCLouvain: Circular economy and its development, design thinking and impact assessment and policy-oriented activities to support innovation in Belgium.
- Innoviris: as the regional funding agency supporting R&I, local priorities and existing mechanisms related with providing support to citizens, companies, research institutions and non-profit organisations in the BCR.

During the Empathizing stage, local project partners made use of structured conversation techniques to lead multiple dialogue sessions towards the achievement of a shared vision. The objectives of these sessions have been to listen to each other's perspectives, insights, ideas, etc.; and to focus on understanding each others' approaches to innovation, citizen engagement, S3, circular economy and RRI processes in the region. Mutual learning and capacity building processes have spontaneously taken place throughout the sessions.

Through the Empathizing stage, the project partners were able to clearly define problems to be tackled in the following steps.

Specificities of the BCR cluster

One of the key issues tackled by project partners during the Empathizing stage was that of the specificities of innovations for circular economy in the BCR territory. Two partners in particular contributed to this discussion, based on their expertise in DT for innovation (MAD - until it pulled out from the project - and ELI-UCLouvain). During presentations and reflections they:

- emphasized that the DT approach makes it possible to structure a collective creation process,

- underlined the dynamic nature of such a DT process, with back-and-forth movements and questioning of supposedly acquired results,
- showed the usefulness of such an approach for innovations in general, whether they concern the design of a new object or an organisational or social innovation.

Key reflections around the governance of innovations in the circular economy field were shared by Innoviris - the Brussels Institute for Research and Innovation. The regional agency is devoted to implementing the Brussels-Capital region's R&I policy and offers funding to support universities, research centres, private companies, local authorities, and non-for-profit actors in developing new products and services. As regional administration in charge of innovation, Innoviris contributes to the regional R&I policymaking process (at the local, national, and European level), such as the definition and implementation of Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3), and works alongside with other RDI regional partners. Based on their expertise, Innoviris raised three key issues which were taken into account and addressed throughout discussions during the Empathizing phase of the process:

- Innoviris would benefit from achieving a better understanding (and measurement of) how the R&I they fund contributes to the local public good. While Innoviris periodically performs a co-design process of key priorities in terms of local public good (through consultations involving the academia, the private sector and local decision makers, and sometimes civil society representatives, performed more or less every three years, in occasion of the renewal of their Regional Plan for Innovation), it does not perform further multi-stakeholder co-design processes throughout the implementation years of its defined strategic priorities, nor periodic assessments of advancements towards the achievement of priorities identified through such multi-stakeholder processes.
- Innoviris experience in running a number of co-created innovation programmes (e.g. the Co-Create funding programme³) has been extremely useful to the agency in getting a deeper understanding of the potential benefits of an RRI approach in R&I. Further RRI elements are also present in the way Innoviris supports R&I, such as for example a strong push for an Open Access approach to research data and publications, as well as fostering more gender balanced research groups and research careers. Citizen engagement is lacking, except in the Co-Create funding programme.

³ <https://innoviris.brussels/fr/co-creation>

- Innoviris supports social innovation, for example through co-funded programmes such as the CoopCity SEEDS and INNOVATE initiatives⁴. The Co-Create funding programme also leads in some cases to the identification of social innovations. Nonetheless, Innoviris explained that many of the social innovations which receive support do not result in tangible outcomes and often lack an appropriate market readiness level to further develop once the funding is over. Besides this, social innovations supported by Innoviris, as well as locally funded R&I in general, lack specific impact assessment processes that connect them to a better understanding of how they contribute to the local public good, or how they address societal needs.

Reflections around the added value of inclusive citizen engagement processes in R&I have been shared by BE participation that has extensive expertise of participatory processes leading to policy recommendations and co-creation in R&I. Key issues raised by BE participation throughout the Empathizing phase include:

- Citizen engagement is often perceived as a process that can sometimes be useful at specific stages of R&I processes, and within specific fields (i.e. applied research vs. basic research) but should not be performed throughout. Through the sharing of multiple examples, from the Belgian territory (such as the CHROMIC project⁵) and beyond, partners' reflections have focused on achieving a better understanding of the potential of citizen engagement in all types of R&I processes and what it can bring to them. This includes for example a better assessment of potential unexpected impacts, but also making sure that the above-mentioned objective of the local public good is better achieved and in line with concrete needs.
- Citizen engagement is also often perceived as a complex and time-consuming process, thus not so relevant to innovation processes which need to be fast and agile. Knowledge sharing with partners has allowed for the identification of examples of citizen engagement which can be performed in the context of R&I - in circular economy and beyond. These examples of citizen engagement show not only that the innovation process is not slowed down, but also that it leads to the identification of additional business opportunities or stronger collaborations which can be beneficial for all actors involved. One example is the Precision Medicine pilot of the SMART-Map project, involving a private company developing innovations in the field of genetic testing⁶.

⁴ <https://coopcity.be/>

⁵ <http://www.chromic.eu/>

⁶ <http://projectsmartmap.eu/precision-medicine/>

The benefits of multi-stakeholder engagement in research & innovation processes

One of the elements which has emerged from discussions among BCR cluster partners is that circular economy, while being nowadays a fashionable term particularly in the context of policy orientations, sometimes still lacks a deep understanding of some of its aspects. Beyond a discussion on the representations of the circular economy and on the names to be used (for example “technological” innovation vs “social” innovation), there is a significant lack of knowledge about the development and stabilization of the circular economy. In particular, it is still often difficult to understand what the real impacts are, beyond the intentions of projects addressing circular economy issues.

“You can know the name of a bird in all the languages of the world, but when you're finished, you'll know absolutely nothing whatever about the bird... So let's look at the bird and see what it's doing — that's what counts. I learned very early the difference between knowing the name of something and knowing something.”

Richard P. Feynman, "What Do You Care What Other People Think?": Further Adventures of a Curious Character, 1988.

The work carried out in the first stage of the cluster processes emphasized the importance of fully understanding what is presented as a changing innovation from an economic, social, environmental and public health perspective. However, in many cases, for circular innovation, these effects are not intuitive. For example, the transfer of industrial plastic waste (coming from construction and building renovation sites) to a civil society association which re-uses it and transforms it into a product (such as for example handbags) is called a social innovation in the circular economy. This social innovation consists in the reuse of materials to reduce the amount of waste, although waste streams such as the industrial ones are often subject to strict rules in terms of disposing and recycling. Potential impacts of such types of social innovation processes are often not taken into account. For example, in this case the re-used industrial waste becomes a product (handbags) which enters new consumption streams, such as for example people's houses. The dissemination and dispersion of households' waste streams when compared to the management of industrial waste can potentially do more harm than benefits to the environment. In this example, one of the unforeseen effects of the innovation is to postpone the problem of recycling and shift its responsibility to households, outside of the regulations that target industrial waste. Based on such examples, and on an historical perspective of the evolution of the circular economy from its beginnings to the present day, the Brussels project partners in their DT journey have identified a first key problem to be addressed: the impacts of an innovation.

Other examples which were exchanged throughout the cluster discussions – not necessarily related to the circular economy in the BCR – also showed that the issue of broad impacts assessment is an important one. The DT's methodology and the Empathize phase made it possible for partners to agree that the analysis of the impacts and their evaluation is a general problem encountered by agencies that support research and innovation – regardless of whether it is connected with an RRI approach or not. This understanding led to a clearer definition of the problem to be addressed.

Converging towards a definition of a conceptual framework for the BCR pilot activities

Considerations on impacts, along with the above-mentioned specific needs and priorities expressed by Innoviris, and the potential benefits of citizen (and 4-helix in general) engagement showcased by BE participation, led to the key observation that a conceptual framework is needed to better assess and support various types of innovation in the circular economy.

Besides reflections around the issue of impact assessment, two additional key elements contributed to the definition of the cluster's conceptual framework. Both of these elements focused on achieving a better understanding of the roles that different actors, including citizens, play in the development of innovations processes in the circular economy. The two elements are:

1. Based on the cluster experience, it was highlighted that there is a strong technological dimension of innovation in the circular economy. The R&D focuses on the separation, purification and treatment processes which would allow the secondary raw material to reach a quality equivalent to the primary raw material at a competitive market price. The challenge is then to avoid downcycling (the secondary raw material produced by recycling processes is of lower quality than the original raw material) and to enter an upcycling logic through increasingly sophisticated processes (for example: cracking of a polymer into monomers). Citizen engagement in such types of processes is still very limited, due to the lack of understanding of the added value which it could bring to them, as well as the perception that it is too complex to implement. Citizens are often confined to a role of "protesting" when the recycling or recovery technology is suspected of generating risks for the environment or for the public health. They also often carry the burden and responsibility of part of the circular economy process (by, for example, having to dispose of multiple types of waste in the established way) but they are rarely invited to express needs, concerns and expectations around these processes, as well as contribute with their ideas and know-how. This finding is important as it emphasizes the potential role for

citizens to take part in the development and impact assessment phases of an innovation, along with researchers and innovators

2. In line with the first element it was also highlighted that, often restricted to a sectoral vision, the circular economy is seen as a set of activities distinct from society and connected to it only through flows of materials (i.e. waste and secondary raw materials). Even if this vision could be considered as historically and technologically relevant, it is nowadays no longer sufficient to understand “what circular economy does and is”. The integrated vision that BCR cluster partners have therefore decided to adopt regarding circular economy is that of: (i) the extension of the idea of recycling and reusing to macro-objects constituting an urban environment - thus the idea of recycling a territory and not just single objects - and (ii) following this extension, the identification of transversalities between issues specific to the circular economy value chains and societal issues, that were previously at best considered separately and at worst completely ignored. This has led the BCR cluster to think for example about the link between the issue of soil decontamination and the disadvantaged part of the population which often lives on polluted soils.⁷

At this stage of the empathizing phase, the cluster transitioned to focusing on a better understanding of the potential of initiatives and innovations within the circular economy field and ways to build transversality and connections with the society in which such innovations will be coming to life.

Addressing multi-stakeholder engagement in the BCR’s support to R&I: the Define phase

Reflections around one additional element played a key role in particular during the transition from the Empathizing to the Define phases. As part of their activities towards the renovation of their Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) for the period 2021-2027 and their new Regional Innovation Plan⁸, Innoviris launched an online survey in September 2020, open to all local actors (including CSOs). The survey focused on assessing key societal challenges in Brussels, and its outcomes have been taken into account in the definition of strategic priorities. A similar survey was also launched, more or less in the same period, by the Brussels Environment funding agency, assessing Brussels citizens’ views and behaviours towards a resilient city, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic crisis. This survey also had

⁷ See TRANSFORM deliverable D2.3 *Report on cluster-specific societal, geographical, economic and environmental frameworks*, in the section dedicated to the BCR framework.

⁸ <https://innoviris.brussels/regional-innovation-plan>

an expected policy impact, as Brussels Environment is in the process of renovating its PREC (Regional Plan for Circular Economy).

Discussions between cluster partners about this kind of tool, how it was set up, feedback collected and how it is used to inform the ongoing policy definition work, were particularly interesting. They focused on possible forms of citizen engagement, benefits and limitations, and their potential effects on regional innovation support programs. Surveys can be a great starting point into the co-design of regional policies and are often used by regional governments to assess current trends. However, cluster partners underlined how a survey on its own does not fulfil the type of citizen engagement envisaged in Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). In that framework, citizens are seen as key and active actors in the definition and achievement of local objectives. It is thus key to the TRANSFORM pilot activities in Brussels to provide the region with examples of how other forms of citizen engagement can be performed, both during the definition of policy orientations and during their implementation. These processes are leading to stronger empowerment processes for societal actors and shared, sustainable changes on the long-term. It is also key to the cluster pilot activities to envisage and test a systematic form of citizen engagement which moves beyond already existing dedicated spaces such as Living Labs, the Co-Create funding programme, or spot-on surveys. At the moment, these initiatives are the only spaces where citizen engagement seems to have a legitimate place to happen.

Overall the Empathize phase allowed partners to achieve a deep understanding of the specificities of the BCR context and the issues at stake (also summarized in D2.3). The Define phase has thus focused on the definition of an innovative pilot for the cluster activities (described more in details in the following chapters) which can contribute to tackling the following key issues:

- integrate citizen engagement in R&I definition and implementation on a more regular basis
- make the actors of the 4-helix interact, particularly at a very early stage in the life cycle of an innovation
- include continuous assessment of the multiple, articulated, potential ex-ante impacts of an innovation
- assess how the implementation of the three previous points can provide a better understanding of how R&I in the BCR contribute to the co-designed priorities for the local public good.

2.3 Responsibly innovating in circular economy: the path to the Spheres pilot

By considering these issues, members used their expertise to generate a potential solution: the sketch of a prototype or of a pilot.: the sketch of a prototype or of a pilot. The multiple (almost weekly) brainstorming sessions between cluster partners, which also included a detailed revision and understanding of existing regional support mechanisms which present some kinds of citizen engagement or other RRI components, led to the identification of key needs for the strengthening of RRI in the innovation-supporting systems of the BCR. In particular, it clearly showed the need for a structure providing support towards the engagement of 4-helix actors around key issues and innovations in the circular economy. The aim is to show how such a process can lead to the identification of transversal societal issues for the region which can significantly contribute to new, responsible forms of innovation in the territory. Such a structure would allow a horizontal approach linking programs, actors and institutions that differs from the vertical approach by program and/or by institution that is frequently being carried out in BCR, in particular in the field of circular economy.

Key elements of the BCR pilot, which has been called *Spheres* - Collective Intelligence in Innovation, are:

- an original circular economy approach that contributes to the S3 strategy of the BCR and that puts an emphasis on the cross-cutting/transversal impacts that emerge well beyond the restricted framework of recycling, recovery, reuse, etc.;
- facilitated repeated interactions between citizens and the other members (researchers-innovators, entrepreneurs and public decision-makers) of the 4-helix relying on inclusive smart supports, which allows to better identify and understand citizen needs and stakes;
- the co-creation of integrated impact assessment methodology with citizens, developing capacities for mutual understanding and enabling to clarify potential impacts of the R&I and to integrate them into the economic, social and cultural fabric of the region;
- a governance approach of the process of R&I which ensures the legitimacy of its R&I processes through citizen engagement;

- a resulting strong bottom-up approach to R&I that at the micro-level coordinates the choice of R&I projects and hence complement the role of the general objectives defined at regional policies and innovation programs levels.

3. Spheres, the pilot action developed by the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital cluster

Based on reflections and discussions carried out throughout the Empathize and Define steps of the Design-Thinking processes, the BCR cluster has ideated a pilot activity. The pilot will allow strengthening citizen engagement practices (and multi-stakeholder engagement in general) in the governance of regional R&I, while clearly assessing its benefits. Thus, the cluster has designed a pilot under the name of *Spheres* - Collective Intelligence in Innovation, that will implement open and inclusive processes to better connect local research and innovation (R&I) to societal needs while involving 4-helix stakeholders.

One of the key aims of *Spheres* is to provide concrete examples of RRI and its benefits, which can be useful to the BCR to replicate and embed in the future. For this reason, *Spheres* will allow to turn a theoretical concept (that of 4-helix engagement in R&I) into something doable, tangible, understandable and concrete. 4-helix processes can be strongly influenced by their initiators: while they happen more and more often in industrial settings (open innovation), they are still rare in public-funded R&I. Governments and private or academic actors each have interests and constraints that can influence the discussions and the process. The way that *Spheres* intends to set up the 4-helix is as oriented to the benefits of innovation and society as possible and brings together various ways of approaching major societal issues, going beyond the partial visions of each member of this helix.

Concretely, *Spheres* will select a group of innovations (including technological and social innovations, but also basic research) which will be assessed through 4-helix engagement in a fast and agile way. Innovations selected to participate in the pilot will go through a participatory process supported by a digital platform. Within the platform, 4-helix stakeholders will be invited to analyze, make suggestions and bring new forms of legitimate knowledge related to these innovations from their own perspectives. They will do so by joining a carefully facilitated process where they will be asked to reflect upon the wider context and envisage potential variations of the innovation and their respective impacts in different plausible scenarios for the territory at hand.

SPHERES : targeting critical innovations

As shown in the figure above, the pilot will look at critical innovations, that is technological, social and organisational innovations related to the circular economy with strong transversal impacts among fields such as food, energy, management, land use, soft mobility, etc.

Processes in the SPHERES pilot

4-Helix stakeholders

❖ Citizens, private sector, universities, public sector

Bring various forms of legitimate knowledge

Engaging dynamic and carefully facilitated processes

- ❖ Starting from needs fulfilled by the innovation
- ❖ To explore, question, (re)create and legitimate potential links between innovator's choices and:
 1. Collective stakes identified in a 4-helix setting,
 2. Potential creative variations of the innovation
 3. Their respective potential impacts for the territory (in plausible scenarios)

TRANSFORM

17

Overall, when compared to other existing initiatives in the territory, Spheres will have the added value to:

1. Boost the potential of local innovations: while in a typical R&I process researchers and innovators often do not have the opportunity to explore the “wider context” related to what they are focusing on, Spheres will allow them to do so in a simple, agile and inclusive way.
2. Better R&I contribution to the public good: Spheres will boost local innovation in a responsible way, integrating citizens’ visions and needs, while strengthening the transdisciplinarity of approaches and knowledge sharing.
3. Complement existing regional instruments, such as those described in chapter 2.2 of this deliverable.

On the long term, Spheres’ original contribution to the local territory is expected to be:

- TAILORED TO REGIONAL SPECIFICITIES - through its S3 dimension and a deep understanding of the territory, Spheres addresses the current lack of transversalities between know-hows and stakeholder groups. Innovations undergoing at least part of the Spheres process have a stronger potential to reach higher market readiness levels, while also contributing to local priorities and societal needs.
- QUADRUPLE-HELIX GOVERNANCE - Spheres is participatory in its essence: it will be recurrently assessed by local 4-helix actors on its ability to efficiently facilitate the resolution of important problems in the region, while also making a link with international trends and innovations developed within the wider European framework.
- INNOVATIVE INTEGRATED IMPACT ASSESSMENT - by collectively assessing the multiple potential added values that innovations can bring to various stakeholder groups, including citizens, Spheres provides to public and private funders innovative tools to perform multidimensional assessments of potential impacts.
- CERTIFICATION - A certificate will be attributed to critical innovations undergoing the Spheres process and showing a high level of positive impacts in selected relevant dimensions such as environmental, societal acceptability and public health.

Concretely, Spheres will set up an agile and highly tailored 4-helix process aimed at critical innovations in the broad field of circular economy. Based on an assessment of each innovation and its specific needs, Spheres experts will set up a process involving 4-helix stakeholders. The decision of which type of actors to involve (including citizens) will depend on information already available, as well as the level of commitment of the innovation to take on board relevant information emerging from the process.

What does the innovation need from Spheres?

- harnessing of collective intelligence (no certification);

- stronger integrated know-how (no certification);
- Co-created impact assessment approach to be taken into account by the innovation (certification and potential follow-up).

4. Community assessment of the Spheres approach

Following the reflections and discussions carried out throughout the Empathize and Define steps of the Design-Thinking processes, as well as the Ideate phase resulting in the pilot activity, a structure called Spheres, the BCR cluster organised community assessment. It consisted in two virtual workshops organised in March 2021, one with representatives from the triple-helix (non-profit sector, public authorities and the private sector) selected to become part of the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital region Think tank, and one with representatives of the fourth helix, the civil society.

Both workshops were aimed at collecting feedback on the chosen TRANSFORM pilot for the BCR - Spheres. Following a presentation of the TRANSFORM project and its key concepts and a presentation of Spheres, participants in both workshops have been asked, based on their expertise, to think about potential strengths and weaknesses of the chosen approach, as well as assess its utility for the BCR.

In order to make the process less abstract, a final step in both workshops has been the presentation of a real innovation in the field of circular economy, currently being developed by a team of Belgian researchers. Participants have been asked in different ways (in order to make both experts and CSOs representatives at ease with this task) to think about correlations between the innovation and their field of expertise, or between the innovation and potential uses and citizens' needs which could be addressed through it.

4.1 Workshop with Think Tank members

4.1.1 Welcome and workshop introduction

The first workshop organised by the BCR cluster took place on 19 March 2021 and was presented by Marzia Mazzonetto and Maïté Debry (BEpart) and Ignace Adant (ELI-UCLouvain).

Following a brief introduction, workshop participants were invited to join an icebreaker activity which allowed them to introduce themselves in a relaxed environment and referring to both professional and personal highlights.

4.1.2 Agenda

Workshop agenda – 12 March 2021 – 2 to 4pm	
14:00 – 14:20	Welcome and workshop introduction - TRANSFORM and its key concepts.
14:20 – 14:30	Presentation of Spheres, the pilot action developed by the TRANSFORM cluster of the Brussels-Capital Region
14:30 - 14:50	Questions/answers from Think Tank members about Spheres
14:50 – 15:05	Presentation of an example of innovation to be assessed by Spheres
15:05 - 15:30	Questions/answers from Think Tank members about the innovation
15:30 – 16:00	In depth discussion with Think Tank members

4.1.3 Participants

The workshop facilitators and presenters were two BCR partners, BE participation and ELI-UCLouvain. The participants came from five organisations presented in the figure below and listed in the table that follows.

Name	Surname	Organisation	Stakeholder group	Description of the expert
Sylvie	Meekers	Inter-Environnement Wallonie	Non-profit, federation of associations	Demonstrated history of working in waste management, biotechnologies, advocacy. Graduated from UCL, FPMs, Coaching Ways, she is the General Director of Inter-Environnement Wallonie, the federation of environmental associations fighting for better air quality in the city and taking care of protection and restoration of ecosystems, environmental education, citizen cooperatives, sustainable food, and soft mobility. The federation works on the implementation of legislation and solutions to accelerate the ecological & inclusive transition.
Grégoire	Clerfayt	Cabinet de la Secrétaire d'État à la Transition économique et à la Recherche scientifique et Ministre-Présidente de la COCOF	Policy Maker	Economic Transition Advisor' at the Office of Secretary of State Barbara Trachte. He is in charge of organising a process for the development and implementation of the Regional Strategy for Economic Transition for Brussels which will absorb the Regional Plan in Circular Economy.
Roland	Moreau	Club de Rome	Non Governmental Organisations	Administrator of WWF-Belgium ; President of the 'Club of Rome – EU Chapter' and of BE-Planet. Expertise in Circular Economy, Environment and Health and advisor for NGOs.
Aarnout	Ecker	Denuo	Federation of entreprises	25 years of professional experience in advancing the circularity of waste / materials. Working for Denuo, the Belgian federation of companies active in the treatment and recycling of waste. Denuo advises public authorities and producers for the adoption of adequate measures to move towards a circular economy.
Guillaume	Cohen	L'Organisation de coopération et de développement économiques - OCDE	International organisation	Analyst in the «Studies of ODD and B4IG countries» at OECD Centre for Well-Being, Inclusion, Sustainability and Equal Opportunity (WISE). The centre is (i) designing a methodological framework to support and developing the assessment of OECD performances regarding SDGs; (ii) Developing new tools and statistical techniques to deepen the analysis Providing analytical tools to gauge country performances regarding the SDG agenda; (iii) Undertaking empirical research to identify strengths and weaknesses of OECD countries

The members of the Think Tank were selected for their expertise relevant to the activities put in place in the region within the context of the project (circular economy, participatory processes, R&I ecosystem of the region, R&I governance). Beside the listed participants, some experts who were not available on the day of the workshop expressed interest in contributing to the process and being involved in future activities (see deliverable D2.1 List of Think Tank members). More specifically, experts taking part in the workshop represented:

Public authorities, governmental actors:

- Grégoire Clerfayt, Ministerial Office of the Secretary of State for the Brussels-Capital Region, in charge of economic transition & scientific research
- Guillaume Cohen, Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development

NGOs, with experience in R&I:

- Sylvie Meekers from Inter-Environnement Wallonie
- Roland Moreau from Club de Rome

Private sector, enterprises, industry:

- Aarnout Eecker from DENUO

4.1.4 Summary and outcomes of the workshop

The workshop started with an introduction to explain the steps and aims of the session, followed by the description of the TRANSFORM project and its key pillars (see section 1 of this deliverable). The core part of the workshop consisted in:

- the description of the Spheres pilot aiming to conduct open and inclusive processes to better connect local research and innovation (R&I) to societal needs while involving 4-helix stakeholders (see section 3 of this deliverable).
- the collection of feedback from participants on the BCR TRANSFORM pilot, Spheres (see below).
- the presentation of an example of innovation to be assessed by Spheres, an innovation from two Phd students from UCLouvain consisting in a platform of water sensors (see below).
- Discussions and feedback on the water sensors innovation, as a simulation of the process BCR TRANSFORM cluster intends to run through Spheres.

- Conclusions on the innovative pilot of the BCR TRANSFORM cluster, the experimentation of a R&I project testing and next steps

a. Questions/answers and comments from Think Tank members about Spheres

After the presentation of the BCR TRANSFORM pilot, Spheres, the participants discussed the innovative approach and provided feedback on the objective, method and key aspect proposed by the TRANSFORM cluster. The key points of this discussion are presented by theme below:

- **Participation and co-creation in policy-making, how to set them up, at which stage?**

The momentum of this activity is very good. Looking at the recent history of policy-making in Belgium, the practices related to participation and to co-creation have been developed in the 10 last years. Previously, most of the time, when a policy plan was set-up, some experts from the administration were engaged, a study was ordered, and an action plan was produced, resulting from the administration working by itself. Policy-making has evolved significantly these days, taking for example the policy plans that have been developed recently, mainly for the environmental issues, like the *'Good Food Plan'*⁹, the *'waste and resources management plan'*¹⁰, the *'regional circular economy plan'*¹¹ and the *'Strategy for reducing the environmental impact of existing buildings in the Brussels-Capital Region by 2030-2050'*¹². The policy-makers and their supporting teams are defining the strategic and operational objectives up-front, then identify stakeholders, organised by themes or domains, and finally organise discussions with them. It has been a process that has progressed through trial and error. Initially, the consultations were organised at the end of the policy-making process, but it would be interesting to integrate them at the design stage. The more the consultations are organised up-front, the more the inputs become rich and wide, and answer various objectives like the contribution to the common public good, and the multi-dimensional approach.

A key question that remains is **how to set-up these participatory processes**. Policy-makers have tested and learned quite a lot through the past experiments. The governance of

⁹ [Plan Good Food](#)

¹⁰ [Plan de gestion des ressources et déchets](#)

¹¹ [PREC Plan régional d'économie circulaire](#)

¹² [Stratégie de réduction de l'impact environnemental du bâti existant en Région de Bruxelles-Capitale aux horizons 2030-2050](#)

participatory processes is at the heart of this evolution. Setting-up a new way to govern these processes is an innovation in itself. It requires policy-making to be ambitious, realistic, inclusive, convincing for the population and engaging a maximum of actors concerned. The current debate around the necessity to organise participatory processes is oriented towards 'construction' rather than 'resistance' in the context of BCR.

Building the **governance and the organisational aspects of participatory processes** linked to **policy-making**, is, as said above, a very interesting innovation in itself that meets some needs at the level of the BCR region. From a practical perspective, for the design of these processes, it is essential to find a compromise between the cost, the efficiency and the volume of information and contributions that citizen participation enables to produce. There are some limits to co-creation processes and it is not always easy to find this balance.

In the BCR, in relation to circular economy, BE circular is currently the main call for projects supporting innovation¹³. Another programme supporting the production of economical solutions and the '*Transition Strategy of the economy of Brussels*'¹⁴ is put in place by the public authorities. The aim is to implement a participatory process upstream and not at the end of the policy-making cycle. This call for projects for innovation tackling the domain of circular economy will be managed by Innoviris, partner in the TRANSFORM project.

- **Innovation with a societal impact or social innovation**

The focus on social innovation or on innovation with societal impacts presented by the Spheres pilot is of particular interest. Innovation focussing on technology only can be worrying as it can be interpreted and defended by promoters of business as usual. It is interesting to move away from the idea that technology will make it possible to keep a status quo for society.

- **Links with the EU Green Deal**

It is important to make links with the EU Green Deal strategy. The European Green Deal Communication by the president of the European Commission, Ursula Von der Leyen, on 11th of December 2019¹⁵ was very ambitious in terms of socio-ecological transition. The way it has evolved since then, became less ambitious. Spheres as a pilot tackling R&I should defend the Green Deal.

¹³ And more particularly, the call for projects of the Brussels-Capital region '[BE circular](#)'

¹⁴ [Stratégie de transition de l'économie bruxelloise à l'horizon 2030 – Go4Brussels 2030](#)

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/speech_19_6749

The systemic approach taken by Patrick Corsi and Jacques de Gerlache brings an interesting take on the Green deal that Spheres should look at¹⁶.

- **The systemic approach:**

The Macroscope concept by Joël de Rosnay published in 1975 is a concept raising the question: ‘*What do ecology, the economic system, the business, the city, the organism, the cell have in common?*’ The answer is nothing, if they are examined with the usual instrument of knowledge, the analytical approach. A lot, if going beyond this classic approach to bring out the main rules of organisation and regulation of all these "systems". It seems the taxonomic reasoning in silos is still predominant and methodologies fostering transversality are still underrepresented. In that context, Spheres is really interesting.

TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital cluster comments:

The cluster is linking with the Green Deal and consider it a very important point. Many calls for proposals of the Green Deal are focusing on participatory activities. In addition, the pilot activity put in place by the regional cluster of BCR is taking the ‘Missions’, the EU strategy into account. The partners involved in the cluster are collaborating with the EC, that is adopting this Mission oriented approach, from which the Green Deal resulted. BE participation has had a number of interactions with the EC for the first phase of the implementation of the Mission called *Climate-neutral* and *Smart cities*. BE participation and Innoviris have collaborated on the implementation of this mission for Brussels.

b. Presentation of an example of innovation to be tested by Spheres

The next step of the workshop consisted in the presentation of an example of Research and Innovation and how the BCR TRANSFORM cluster could test it through its pilot, Spheres. The objective was to try out the process and to generate a discussion around this innovation with the 4-helix representatives.

The TRANSFORM BCR cluster aimed to explain a part of the process of this innovation could be handled by Spheres in the future, with the contribution of multiple knowledge and contents that can be integrated in the project. The people involved in Spheres, from the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital cluster, have the scientific and the citizen engagement perspectives that could develop an action strategy applied to this innovation.

¹⁶ Aiming at a sustainable society for shared future welfare, a systemic interpretation of the European Union Green Deal: <https://www.clubofrome.eu/a-systemic-interpretation-of-the>

The Phd R&I project presented on that day consisted in a lab on a chip with water sensors. The initiators of this project, Margo Hauwaert and Grégoire Le Brun of UCLouvain presented their project¹⁷. The first figure (1.) from the slides, available below, represents the water cycle and provides details on how adequate access to quality water is crucial for life and an important socio-economic catalyst. Unfortunately, not all citizens are fortunate enough to have even access to safe drinking water. In addition, the pressures on resources are increasing significantly. In many ways, the water cycle needs to be better managed. When it comes to better management of the water cycle, there is a need for knowledge about quality. For example, before consumption, citizens must be sure that the water is reliable. In Belgium this guarantee is given by the water network provider, and it is mainly trusted by citizens. But this is not the case in all countries. It is also crucial to test when water is released into nature, for example through industrial effluents. Good environmental quality is necessary to allow circular use of water.

There is a need for water quality security that is exemplary and coherent. The R&I project proposes to contribute to the management of the water cycle through a water quality measurement tool that is accessible, low cost, easy to use and adaptable for a large number of parameters and uses.

With this technology different uses are possible in the water cycle. As can be seen in the second figure (2.), the scope of uses is large. One possible scenario is medical diagnostics, for example to detect pathogens in water. This is applicable both when there is no network (e.g. setting up a refugee camp) but also when dealing with an epidemic of diseases transmitted by water vectors. It is therefore essential that medical teams, but also citizens, have rapid access to a diagnosis.

Since it was designed as a lab on a chip (integrating the water sensors *stricto sensu*), it can be used to test water in industrial effluents and agricultural systems (see figure 3. below). Yet, it still needs a solution that holds a number of characteristics like frequency, cheap price and rapidity.

Sensors generate data. The envisioned innovation can provide democratic access to data and therefore knowledge about the water cycle to citizen groups and can answer some needs such as accessibility, manipulability, and affordability (see figure 4. below). It enables

¹⁷ École polytechnique de Louvain, PhD thesis, , '*Towards electro-chemical characterisation of paper-based sensors and usage perspectives Responsible water quality sensor*' design, Author: Margo HAUWAERT Supervisor: Jean-Pierre RASKIN Readers: Ignace ADANT, Marc DEBLIQUY, Grégoire LE BRUN Academic year 2019–2020 Master [120] in Electro-mechanical Engineering - retrieved from Internet on 10 March 2021: https://www.foundationfuturegenerations.org/sites/www.foundationfuturegenerations.org/files/2021_mtaengineering_15_tfe_margohauwaert.pdf

citizens to participate in the management of the water cycle and, when necessary, to even emancipate themselves from other formal or informal institutions and to further implement change in the organisation of their community.

This lab-on-a-chip is a low-cost platform, providing various functionalities, i.e. the different blocks are useful for an effective and beneficial use. It can be used by scientists accustomed to water quality measurements but also by citizens wondering about the quality of the water they drink. The platform offers integrated connectivity functions, which, for example, allow these measurements to be taken with a simple smartphone. It allows direct transmission and sharing of measurements with an associated database, for scientists or citizens depending on the application.

In the figure (6.) below, it can be seen that one of the crucial aspects of this platform is the versatility of its use. The mix of detection technologies used makes it possible to take advantage of the strengths of each technology, and to broaden the spectrum of use. As shown in the figure, the technical blocks make it possible to study both physico-chemical parameters of water (pH, conductivity, salinity, and mineral parameters, heavy metals, etc.), but also for the detection of biological pathogens.

This modular approach allows the user to select the parameters they want to be able to detect, and can adapt very quickly to many types of situations, making it possible to potentially respond to emergency situations. The technologies used for this platform offer very rapid R&D opportunities, and can be updated very quickly, for example to meet the needs of Covid detection in water to prevent the spread of the virus.

As can be seen in figure 7., the use of a connected platform can provide water quality results rapidly taking local and international standards into account, allowing rapid management and decision-making. The interest, for professionals of health, industry and environmental actors, is the production of a reliable mass of measurements, with a display of the results in real time and at the place of sampling, configurable according to the desired use.

Finally, the ergonomics of this platform has been a priority while designing it (figure 8.). With the integration of the various functionalities mentioned above, an easy use is made possible to any citizen, through a live display of the results, validated by controls and integrated connectivity. This way, citizens of both developed countries and developing countries will have more information on the quality of the water allowing them to better understand and better manage their water resources.

The generation of a reliable community-owned database, generated by citizens and accessible to all, citizens and scientists, is one of the greatest advantages offered by this measurement platform.

c. Questions/answers from Think Tank members about the innovation project

The feedback collected through this simulation of the process the TRANSFORM BCR cluster intends to implement through Spheres, a testing of an innovation project, were the following:

- **Data privacy:**

With this type of immediate technology that enables filling databases with a large number of data, the question of data privacy is key. The question 'Is the diffusion of information and data always positive?' is key to raise and the social responsibility aspect should be taken into account.

- **Data validation and interpretation:**

Experiments in which citizens are involved, receive captors or sensors and have direct access to information are really interesting to see how the interaction between citizens and access to information functions and to analyse possible drifts. Information technology and data collecting technology are developing fast, becoming smaller and smaller and can acquire many functions.

The question of data validation, data interpretation and understanding are key for this type of technology and interaction with citizens. There might be an issue with raw data not well interpreted and false information being spread. To interpret scientific data correctly, some explanation on the nature of these data is necessary and it is important to take this into account when data is directly available to a large public. The data should be available and understandable without advanced scientific knowledge.

- **Citizen trust:**

Another question is the citizens' trust toward the information provided. Some citizens could refuse to be explained how to interpret data.

The question of the initiator of data sharing is also key. If the actor providing the access to data is an enterprise that causes pollution, the trust within the group of citizens accessing the information will probably be very low and if it is coming from an institution working on environmental issues, very high.

- **Transparency and early engagement of citizens:**

Transparency is fundamental for trust and reliability as well as the question of the initiator that manages and pays the experiment. An element of the experiment that could have an impact on citizen trust, is the location of the captors for pollution analysis. This means that the engagement of citizens, upstream in the process, when all the experiment's elements are defined and before measures start to be taken, is fundamental. Involving citizens while data is already available and the experiments are running can be more controversial with people already positioning themselves pro or cons, with less nuance and consistency. Taking the time to make a research project known and understood by groups of citizens from the start gives the project a greater chance to avoid drifts and controversy.

- **Participatory processes at design stage:**

An interesting element of Spheres is the integration of citizen participation at the design phase, rather than the classical approach followed by researchers and innovators. Most of the time, they are answering calls for projects defining the research question, without considering the needs from society. The participatory processes such as proposed by Spheres would enable to enrich the decision-making for programmes financing the development of R&I projects in the domain of circular economy at the urban scale.

Additional question to the participants in the workshop:

To nurture further the discussions with the workshop participants, the cluster members raised an additional question:

What do you think are the possible applications of this technology?

- In the BCR for example. A data is interesting if compared to a standard or to the evolution of a standard. It could also bring anxiety, and influence trust. Before bringing a new system of measurement it should be accepted by a majority of the population.
- In locations where access to safe water is limited or uncertain, providing people with such cheap sensors should be accompanied by some information on the impact of poor-quality water on health. Under such conditions, it could help to tackle one important problem arising when trust in the quality of water is based solely on its taste or on beliefs that have no scientific basis.
- To reduce the consumption of water in plastic bottles. If citizens of a city are better informed about the water quality and the impact of low-quality water from an

organoleptic point of view it could shift the demand for water from bottled water to tap water.

- At the opposition of this view, one should also take into account that consumption choice is not always objective, and highly influenced by marketing.
- In Flanders, there has been a large study on water quality and consumption which had a very low impact on people's habits. Additional data do not specifically impact citizens. One must also anticipate another possible form of use where the consumer only uses the sensor once and then turns away from it.
- The use of a smartphone combined with the captors, from an ecological point of view does not seem to be the main issue. Everybody has a smartphone already. The issue is more related to the captor in itself. If it is affordable and a large number of people buy it, to test water at home a few times and then never use it again. The environmental impact of the production of a technological device that will be rarely used is much higher than the advantage of being able to test water.

d. Workshop conclusions:

The last part of the workshop was dedicated to conclude the two main steps of the workshop. These two steps were:

- the presentation and feedback collection on Spheres, the innovative pilot proposed by the BCR TRANSFORM cluster, aiming to conduct open and inclusive processes to better connect local research and innovation (R&I) to societal needs while involving 4-helix stakeholders
- the presentation and feedback collection on an example of innovation to be tested by this pilot, an innovation from two Phd students from UCLouvain consisting in a platform of water sensors.

The members of the BCR TRANSFORM pilot commented on the approach they wish to develop with Spheres and applied it to the example of innovation. They also commented the discussions that occurred around this example during the workshop and the key added-value they bring to R&I:

- Understanding impacts upfront that could have been ignored, is a key aim of Spheres. The aim is to show the added-value of 4-helix involvement and collective intelligence on R&I. Spheres will try to develop some indicators and evaluation methodology to analyse this added-value. Spheres is taking the role of a missing relay to evaluate this type of methodology.

- Spheres' method of work when assessing this type of innovation would be to dive into the water problematic, analysing the areas of use of the captor, water consumption by citizens, like tap water drinking and its various consequences for society.
- The exploration of collective intelligence brings information on motivations and concerns of the public. Understanding what people are worried or curious about helps in having a better grasp of the ecosystem around the project. It is really important to use this information and the researchers/innovators can capitalize on it.
- The question of the usefulness of giving citizens access to some scientific data, information, e.g. on air pollution data, is an important one. If citizens have access to this information but no impact on the environmental issue, it can cause frustration. Data sharing with a large public should be accompanied with a sociological, philosophical and psychological reflection.
- Involving various disciplines as for example sociologists in this type of experiments gives a very interesting perspective as they look at aspects such as the impact of the data collection on the behaviour of groups of citizens. If people access information and data that show diverse problems of pollution but do not believe the situation can change, it can influence them greatly, causing for example house moving.

4.2 Workshop with civil society organisations representatives

4.2.1 Agenda and aim of the workshop

The aim of this workshop was to collect feedback and ideas from the nonprofit sector¹⁸, representing the 'Civil Society' part of the 4-helix, around the innovative approach developed by the BCR cluster. The objective was also to launch the first phase of civil society engagement for the BCR TRANSFORM pilot, starting with non-profit organisations anchored in the region before the direct engagement of groups of citizens. The workshop was the occasion for the cluster leader (BEpart), a non-profit organisation experienced in collective intelligence to initiate the co-design of the citizen engagement process with other actors from the sector in the region.

Workshop agenda – 19 March 2021 – 2 to 4pm	
14:00 – 14:30	Welcome and introduction
14:30 – 14:50	Presentation of the TRANSFORM project, the pilot activity Spheres - Collective Intelligence in Innovation and explanation of the role and contribution expected from members of civil society and citizens
14:50 - 15:15	Questions / answers: pilot activities and the role of civil society in Spheres .
15:15 – 15:50	Discussion about the two following questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Is there a project that comes to mind, in the context of your associative or other work, which you think could benefit from Spheres? Would you like to share it with us?• How to ensure citizen participation - particularly in the context of the health crisis and the digitization of participatory processes?
15:50 – 16:00	Next steps

¹⁸ The Civil Society words (or concept) are not widely used in the Belgian context and by extension in the Brussels-Capital region. The organisations working with citizens and representing their voices, defending their rights and engaging them in participatory activities are referred to as 'secteur non-marchand' or 'monde associatif', which can be translated by 'non-profit sector'.

4.2.2 Participants

The workshop facilitators and presenters were the two BCR cluster partners, BEpart and ELI-UCLouvain. The participants came from nine associations (non-profit organisations) based in the BCR presented in the figure below and in the table that follows. The associations engaged in the workshop were selected for their links with the priority domains that Innoviris selected for the new Smart Specialisation Strategy - S3 (2021-2027)¹⁹ and more particularly the ones that have been chosen for the BCR TRANSFORM cluster.

The associations represented were from the following fields of activities: social innovations, health, well-being, environment, circular economy, environment, green IT, eco-citizenship, sustainable development, sustainable food, urban agriculture, sustainable agricultural and rural development, food security, urban development and social economy.

The associations represented were also selected for their experience in fields and methodologies related to participatory processes including: co-creation processes, multi-stakeholder engagement, citizen participation, participatory management of citizens, participatory democracy, democratic governance and decision-making, youth engagement and popular education.

¹⁹ See section 1.2 of this deliverable, on the key pillars of TRANSFORM, more specifically the pillar related to S3.

Organisation	Contact Name	Contact Surname	URL	Working themes of the association
Premisse	Zehra	Gokburun	https://premise.be/	Health, Well-being, Food,
Inter-Environnement Bruxelles asbl	Cataline	Sénéchal	https://www.ieb.be/	Environment, citizen participation
City Mine(d)	Jim	Segers	http://beta.citymine.d.org/	Urban development, citizen participation, cocreation process
CF2D	Bernard	Goffinet	https://cf2d.be/	Social economy, circular economy, environment, Green IT
MJ Verte	Julie	Jacobs	https://miverte.be/	Eco-citizenship, sustainable development, environnement, Youth engagement
Refresh Bruxelles	Amandine	Vandormael	https://refreshbxl.com/qui-sommes-nous	Participatory management of citizens, sustainable food, urban agriculture
Periferia	Deborah	Hobe	https://periferia.be/	Participatory democracy, multistakeholders engagement, governance, decision-making
Collectif Stratégies Alimentaires	Jonas	Jaccard	http://www.csa-be.org/	Sustainable agricultural and rural development as well as food security
Urban ecology	Simon	De Muynck	https://urban-ecology.be/#equipe	Social innovations, multi stakeholder engagement, transformative projects, popular education, transition of complex systems, valuation of organic matter, urban trees and soils.

4.2.3 Summary and outcomes of the workshop

The workshop was introduced by an icebreaker activity to allow participants to introduce each-other with an informal activity.

The next point was an introduction to explain the steps and aims of the session, followed by some contextualisation with the description of the TRANSFORM project and its key pillars (see section 1 of this deliverable). The core part of the workshop consisted in:

- the description of the Spheres pilot aiming to conduct open and inclusive processes to better connect local research and innovation (R&I) to societal needs while involving 4-helix stakeholders (see section 3 of this deliverable).
- presentation of examples of projects in the domain of circular economy or urban development were presented to explain the relevance of introducing 4-helix engagement and participatory processes in general (see below).
- the collection of feedback from non-profit organisations representatives on the pilot and on the set-up of collective intelligence with groups of citizens (see below).

The two examples of projects in the domain of circular economy or urban development are visible in the figure below, one referring to a project consisting in the recycling of construction tarps into hand-bags and the other to the introduction of urban agriculture in a neighborhood of Brussels.

First example: Tarps have been used when buildings of the 'Grand Place' of Brussels were renovated. These tarps represented the buildings that were hidden during renovation. A public agency working on design & innovation proposed to create nice hand-bags out of the recycled tarps to be sold to the public. An issue appeared while the project was already running and bags were already sold. The plastic material from which these tarps are made is complex to recycle, a process, normally done by specialised enterprises. With the plastic used for consumer goods, the issue that emerged was that a highly polluting plastic was spread around with no possibility to be recycled. This example was presented to show how engaging the 4-helix, including representatives from the private sector specialised in recycling processes and scientists aware of the nature of the material, would have allowed to avoid this issue.

Exemples d'innovations qui pourraient bénéficier de SPHERES...

La prairie-lisière du Rouge-Gorge : un site naturel exceptionnel menacé

Bruxelles Environnement (l'Institut bruxellois de gestion de l'environnement) est en train de détruire un des plus riches sites naturels de la Forêt de Soignes sous prétexte de développer l'agriculture urbaine. Des riverains s'y opposent.

Second example: A project of urban agriculture in the area of Brussels called the 'Rouge-Gorge' in Watermael-Boitsfort. In this example, the point was to raise some reflections on the fact that engaging the 4-helix, here, more particularly the citizens, would have benefited the initiators of the project. A significant lack of adhesion to the project from the residents of the area appeared after the decision was taken to transform a prairie with an interesting biodiversity into fields for urban agriculture.

a. Questions/answers and comments from participants about Spheres

The participants were asked:

- to provide open feedback on TRANSFORM and Spheres and to reflect on the needs and interests this pilot could answer.
- to reflect on projects in the context of their work, which could benefit from TRANSFORM and Spheres.
- to provide their takes on citizen engagement and how to ensure their participation - particularly in the context of the health crisis and the digitization of participatory processes.

The feedback collected is summarised here:

MJ verte: The participatory, global and cross-dimensional aspects of the Spheres pilot is very relevant to the work of the association, a collectif that is co-created with its members and its target public (youth centres and animators). The co-creation process aims to instill principles of eco-citizenship, sustainable development and circular economy. Starting from general objectives, the participatory process leads to very useful and meaningful results. The approach presented by Spheres, involving all stakeholders but also beneficiaries from

innovation projects to take the societal dimension of the project into account is really interesting. Innovations that go through a 4-helix and collective intelligence processes are real innovations, bringing an added-value to the society, with long-term promising results.

A need and an interest identified is to take part in reflection on collective intelligence and participatory processes.

ReFRESH: The questions tackled by the association are at the heart of social innovation. The association is dependent on public funding. It is part of their social business model. When referring to innovation, the main understanding is the creation of new 'things' but an area that really needs innovation are the processes of subsidizing authorities and the agreements that link associations to funding. They are disconnected to realities on the ground and much focussed on controlling how the public funds are spent. The functioning of associations are impacted by these funding instruments and confronted with a certain lack of flexibility related to public administration processes dealing with social innovation in general. The relation with public administration on that matter are mainly defined by control and bureaucratie. Activity plans are restrained by these rigid frameworks and associations struggle to think in circularity.

On another matter, the association is really interested by the multidimensional approach defended by the Spheres pilot. The activities of this association and its social project are touching upon many domains including the socio-professional integration, employment, the ecological impact of their activities, etc... The understanding of circular economy as proposed by the BCR TRANSFORM cluster, holds advantages that can relate nicely to this preoccupation to embrace a multidimensional approach. Its understanding is linked to the territory and taking the societal realities and citizens needs related to its implementation into account.

A need identified by this association is an innovation that would consist in the creation of an agile tool to help manage funding for social innovation and projects resulting from these financial support, where the human is at the centre.

An initiative that could benefit from Spheres is LAGUM, a FEDER project which consists in the creation of an educational space and experimental production market gardener on part of the roof of the Colruyt supermarket, located rue Gray in Ixelles, in collaboration with ReFRESH, the Municipality of Ixelles and ULB. There are two axes in this project: multifunctionality of urban agriculture and sustainability. The researcher Francisco Davila (ULB) leads a participatory research that could benefit from a collaboration with Spheres. A

memorandum for the recognition of the multifunctionality of sustainable urban agriculture, which brought together different actors around the functions of Brussels agricultural projects (ecology, biodiversity, social, health, training, integration, etc.) has been established and holds a shared observation: the need for understanding systemic approach of such projects to provide appropriate, efficient, coherent and therefore sustainable public support. The signatories of the memorandum call for the creation of a financing tool structural and decompartmentalized for projects with a broad societal impact and propose that this tool be either co-constructed in consultation between the project leaders, the administrations concerned and political authorities.

Inter-Environnement Bruxelles: IEB works with a large number of neighborhood committees that are members of their Federation. They are engaged in participatory processes working on what they call 'micro-territories'. These committees noticed that, when engaged in participatory processes organised by decision-makers, the decisions were already taken and their contribution was really limited.

The association highlighted the fact that citizens available to take part in participatory processes must have a certain security from various points of view including the financial, educational and affective aspects. These are often conditions for citizens to be able to engage in activities that are touching domains beyond their private sphere.

An initiative from which lines of collaboration could emerge with the TRANSFORM pilot for BCR, in the domain of circular economy, is a study that IEB will finalise in the coming months. This analysis will identify obstacles appearing in a waste recycling project that did not particularly develop well. It was a project of co-management of waste by local merchants in a district of Brussels. The main target public were people with low-income (compared to the local average income), newcomers migrants not always speaking french or flemish. An interesting observation has been that the low level of participation from these merchants was not related to a lack of understanding of the project. When provided with translators, most of the merchants were totally able to argue on their choices to not take part in the waste sorting process and their opinion was really interesting to take into account.

Periferia: They have experience implementing participatory processes, for example citizens panels organised at the level of the region. They are working with groups of citizens that are usually under-represented in citizen engagement and are implementing various strategies to ensure their participation in online engagement and face-to-face interviews.

They are providing prepaid Internet cards, access to computers in physical spaces respecting COVID-19 restrictions, to welcome participants. This has been done in collaboration with other associations to have various physical spaces available in various locations of the region.

4.3 Summary of key outcomes of community assessment

Contributions from Think Tank members:

The main outcomes of the community assessment of the Spheres approach organised through a workshop are summarized below:

- **Setting-up participatory processes from the design stage for innovation policy making is key in BCR and policymakers could benefit from the TRANSFORM pilot Spheres.** Most of the time, participatory processes are organised at the end of the policy-making process in BCR, but it would be interesting to integrate them at the design stage. The more the consultations are organised up-front, the more the inputs become rich and wide, and answer various objectives like the contribution to the common public good. Setting-up a new way to govern these processes is an innovation in itself. For these processes to have a certain amplitude, it is essential to design them in a realistic way finding a compromise between the cost, the efficiency and the volume of information and contributions that citizen participation enables to produce.
- **The focus on social innovation or innovation with societal impacts presented by the Spheres pilot is of particular interest.** When innovation is understood in a more restrictive sense, focusing on technology only, initiated by promoters of business as usual, the multi-dimensional aspects and the link to societal needs are missing.
- **The multidimensional approach defended by the Spheres concept, the pilot of the TRANSFORM BCR is key to transformation.** It seems the taxonomic reasoning in silos is still predominant in Brussels' R&I and methodologies fostering transversality are still underrepresented. In that context, Spheres is really interesting.
- **Recommendation to make links with the EU Green Deal.** Spheres as a pilot tackling R&I should defend the Green Deal and its high ambition in terms of socio ecological transition.

Contributions from Civil Society organisations:

The main outcomes of the community assessment of the Spheres approach organised through a workshop are summarized below:

- There is an **overall interest and willingness** of CSOs to take part in sessions on collective intelligence and participatory processes to be applied to their project coordination processes and their own governance.
- Despite their interest to contribute to the Spheres pilot, CSOs shared a common feeling of **not being used to being asked to take part in innovation processes**, apart from those that are directly initiated by them. This shows that there is still a strong disconnection between innovation settings and civil society.
- **The need for more agility** in the management of the funding for social innovation and projects resulting from these financial support, where the human is more at the centre.

5. Conclusions and steps ahead

Summary of activities leading to the needs definition

Two types of activities have been key to the definition of the needs that the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital's pilot aims to address:

- a Design Thinking (DT) approach applied to the analysis of Innoviris' needs in order to implement stronger citizen engagement approaches in the way it designs and supports the implementation of one of its key S3 priorities: innovations for sustainable development and circular economy. Key steps in this process have been: a) a mutual learning and capacity building phase (called "Empathizing" and "Defining", in the DT journey), involving project partners and leading to a shared understanding of current RRI strengths and weaknesses in the region; b) a mapping exercise of existing regional co-design and support mechanisms which allow for some types of multi-stakeholder engagement (such as the Co-Create funding programme, Living Labs, CoopCity and online consultations during the drafting of the new Regional Plan for Innovation); c) a gaps analysis of the way circular economy is supported and develops in the region, with a specific focus on social innovation and interactions (or the lack of) between fields related to circular economy (such as energy, food, water, soil and urbanism). This process and its outcomes are described in Chapter 2 of this report.
- as a further step in the Design Thinking approach (the "Ideation" phase), the definition of shared objectives for the activities of the TRANSFORM Brussels pilot, which has taken shape under the name of Spheres - Collective Intelligence in Innovation (described in Chapter 3). The cluster has at first clearly outlined how Spheres can contribute to address the R&I needs emerged during the mutual learning and capacity building phase, while also boosting the region's RRI commitment. Secondly, it has performed an exercise of community assessment of its pilot idea, collecting feedback and ideas from 15 local representatives of the 4-helix (CSOs, research institutions, public authorities and the private sector). This has happened through two online workshops, which have been described at length in Chapter 4 of this report.

One key aspect of the "Ideation" phase, both for cluster partners discussion and for the community assessment processes, has been the opportunity to concretely test how the

proposed TRANSFORM pilot would work in a real setting. To achieve this, the collaboration with a real critical innovation in the field of circular economy has been very beneficial. Throughout discussions among project partners, as well as in the workshops with 4-helix stakeholders, Margo Hauwaert and Grégoire Le Brun of UCLouvain, initiators of a Phd R&I project focused on developing a “lab on a chip” water sensor, have agreed to present their innovation, in order to provide a real-case scenario for the testing of the Spheres pilot. Both TRANSFORM and the innovators have benefitted from this experiment:

- the innovators had the opportunity to deepen into transversalities linked with their innovation, including potential uses of their product by unexpected target groups, links with current public health issues, considerations on the sustainability of certain business opportunities, as well as ways in which citizen science could provide an excellent model to address data collection and data management issues linked to the innovation
- cluster and 4-helix members had the opportunity to assess how Spheres could work in terms of performing a first overall assessment of critical innovations at their prototyping stage; how knowledge sharing in a well facilitated environment can lead to an agile first round of knowledge sharing which can be beneficial to the innovation, without slowing down the innovation itself, and in a fully virtual environment; how citizen engagement should be envisaged in such process, distinguishing between already available information (i.e. citizens’ perception of tap water quality and safety in Brussels) and potential beneficial information emerging from interactions with citizens (i.e. a focus group to better understand citizens’ concerns around water quality, and what type of data sharing they would be willing to do in exchange for better access to information around water quality).

Spheres: addressing co-designed needs

The TRANSFORM pilot Spheres is clearly addressing some issues that have been identified - both by the public agency involved in the project (Innoviris), by project partners BE participation and ELI-UCLouvain, and by the 4-helix representatives involved in the workshops - as key to a future implementation of S3 priorities in the territory that is more in line with RRI components and the achievement of a local and global public good. In particular:

- Spheres addresses a key need of the Brussels region, that of making its participatory processes in R&I in general, and in circular economy in particular, more integrated, inclusive, useful and sustainable. As affirmed by one of the Think Tank members,

“Building the governance and the organisational aspects of participatory processes linked to policy-making, is a very interesting innovation in itself that meets some needs at the level of the BCR region. (...) It requires policy-making to be ambitious, realistic, inclusive, convincing for the population and engaging a maximum of actors concerned.” Civil Society representatives also agreed that *“The approach presented by Spheres, involving all stakeholders but also beneficiaries from innovation projects to take the societal dimension of the project into account is really interesting. Innovations that go through a quadruple helix and collective intelligence process are real innovations, bringing an added-value to the society, with long-term promising results.”* Spheres will show not only that such processes are possible, but also that they can be easily implemented. It will empower citizens to take an active and engaged role in the shaping of collective futures, and the changes they require.

- An key byproduct of strengthening participatory processes will be that of anticipating unforeseen (societal) impacts of R&I, raising societal acceptance of and engagement with environmental challenges and innovations in circular economy, and providing a clearer understanding and measurements of how Brussels-funded R&I contributed to a collectively defined public good.
- Spheres also addresses needs which are relevant to the aims of the TRANSFORM project and therefore the priorities set by the EC, such as for example the mainstreaming of RRI beyond dedicated sylos where co-creation and citizen engagement are already allowed to take place, or spontaneously take place despite not being specifically required. The TRANSFORM Brussels cluster pilot is also in line with the Horizon Europe Mission-oriented approach, by integrating co-design and co-creation approaches within the implementation of concrete mission projects which will contribute to the achievement of the circular economy mission at regional level, but also the climate change and the climate-neutral and smart cities Missions at European level. Spheres contribution is also in line with many of the key priorities set out in the recent round of Green Deal calls, such as for example the need for stronger transversalities between disciplines, the need to take action at the individual and collective level, the need for stronger capacities for citizen deliberation and participation, as well as better data sharing and interoperability.
- by performing an impact assessment of its activities, SPHERES will also provide useful tools to the region in terms of showing the added value of strengthening citizen engagement in R&I. This addresses one key point emerged in cluster meetings, that is the lack of measurements of the innovation potential of the region

that take into account RRI components such as citizen engagement, besides standard ones such as patents or job creation.

Steps ahead

There are two key challenges to the success of the Spheres implementation, as assessed by both project partners and participants of the two workshops, which will need to be carefully addressed in the coming months: its costs and long-term sustainability. These will be addressed by cluster partners in two ways. Particular attention will be dedicated to the identification of agile processes, established case by case, as well as the creation of a community of practice around Spheres (which has already started with the engagement of 4-helix actors in the two workshops) which can be easily mobilised when assessing innovations. Design-Thinking will be key to this objective, as it represents a dynamic tool which can be easily adapted to the specific context and needs of the innovations and the 4-helix environment. Throughout the Spheres implementation, special attention will also be paid to ensuring its sustainability in the long term. The key aim of the TRANSFORM project being for public authorities to be directly involved in the project activities and benefit from them, leading to institutional changes which bring changes on the long term, it is expected that Innoviris will make use of Spheres also beyond the duration of the project, for example by finding ways to embed its 4-helix approach in support and evaluation processes of regional innovations. Besides this, project partners are already actively exploring future funding streams, both at the European and the local public/private level, to guarantee Spheres' sustainability beyond the duration of the project. These will be described more in detail in D5.2 : Strategic Roadmaps for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through design thinking for social innovation within S3 priorities (M34).

Based on all the above-mentioned preparatory work and the validation received from the local 4-helix community, the Brussels-Capital cluster will now proceed with the implementation of the pilot activities (M16 to M34). Concretely, in the coming months the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital cluster members will:

- select innovations in the field of circular economy which are critical to boost the regional innovation potential and could lead to significant (and often unaccounted for) societal impacts. The selection will be performed through an open call. Selected innovations will be both innovations emerging in research institutions and the private sector, but also bottom-up social innovations suggested by citizens. Innovations at various stages of their development will be assessed, with a

preference to innovation which are still at an early stage of implementation (i.e. the prototyping phase). The assessment of such innovations will allow the testing and refinement of the way Spheres works, while also allowing to evaluate its efficacy and the added values brought by iterative citizen engagement processes.

- build a community of practice around Spheres, bringing together various types of expertise, and with a special focus on the involvement of Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and their citizens, who are rarely invited to share their collective knowledge around innovations that are mostly presented to them as end-users.
- through the 4-helix assessment of the selected innovations, and a sound Design-Thinking process, set up an agile and sustainable approach that will on the long term make Spheres result into a key asset for Innoviris and the Brussels-Capital region
- further develop the impact assessment process of both Spheres, and the 4-helix processes it supports, through the definition of a methodology allowing the co-creation of impact assessment with the quadruple-helix members. It's aim will be to create collective learning on selected societal stakes and to be able to share this knowledge.

Bibliography

Brown, T., 2020. IDEO Design Thinking. [online] IDEO | Design Thinking. Retrieved 18 November 2020, from: <https://designthinking.ideo.com/>.

Hasso Plattner Institute of Design, 2010. An Introduction to Design Thinking PROCESS GUIDE [Ebook]. Retrieved 18 November 2020, from <http://web.stanford.edu/~mshanks/MichaelShanks/files/509554.pdf>.

Volpi, V., Opromolla, A. and Medaglia, C., 2019. Analyzing Social Impact Evaluation Tools Applied to Design Thinking: A Proposal for Improving User Experience in Urban Spaces Through Social Innovation. pp.353-362.

Feynman, Richard P., What Do You Care What Other People Think?, 1988, 256 pages, W.W. Norton, ISBN 0-393-02659-0, 2001.

www.transform-project.eu

 @TRANSFORM_eu

 TRANSFORM project group

 TRANSFORM project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement N°872687